

Physico-Chemical Studies of Uranyl Ion Complex with 2-Carboxypyridine *N*-Oxide and Gravimetric Determination of Uranium

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High frequency titrimetric and conductometric studies of uranyl ion complex with 2-carboxypyridine *N*-oxide show that the ratio of uranyl ions and ligands in the molecule, in the pH range 2 to 3, is 1:2. Gravimetric determination of uranium as complex has been found possible within the pH range 2 to 3.8. Correct results have been also obtained by ignition of the complex to oxide. The complex is slightly soluble and in case of very dilute solutions, minimum permissible pH is more than 2.0 (e.g. 2.5 for *M*/150 soln.).

Heller and co-workers¹ have recently studied the complexes of uranium (VI), plutonium (IV), plutonium (VI), zirconium (IV), and beryllium with 2-carboxypyridine *N*-oxide. They have reported that the uranium complex is precipitated quantitatively at pH 2.3 and has the composition $UO_2A_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (*A*=ligand). Lever *et al.*² have studied the complexes of 2-carboxypyridine *N*-oxide with many metals, especially those of the first transition series.

Using high frequency titrimetric and conductometric methods, the authors have found that the molar ratio of the uranyl ion and the *N*-oxide residue in the complex is 1:2, as reported by Heller *et al.*¹ Gravimetric determination of uranium alone and also in presence of some other cations has also been made, using the *N*-oxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

High frequency titrimeter used was a 30 Mc unit, described earlier³. pH measurements were carried out with a Metrohm pH-meter, type E-350 and a Kohlrausch slide-wire conductivity bridge (Leeds and Northrup) was used for conductance measurements. B. D. H., A. R. sample of uranyl nitrate was used for preparing standard solutions of uranium and 2-carboxypyridine *N*-oxide was procured from L. Light & Co., England. All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

Composition of the Complex.—For high frequency titration work, effective component method³ was used. Uranyl salt solution containing an appropriate amount of uranium was taken and the volume was made to about 60 ml. An aqueous solution of 2-carboxypyridine *N*-oxide of such a concentration was added from a microburette that the total volume consumed at the end point was about 5-6 ml. A representative curve is shown in

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 4738.

2. *Ibid.*, 1962, 5262.

3. Kumar and Singh, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1963, 57A, 79.

Fig. 1 (curve A). The initial pH of the aqueous solution was about 3 to 3.2 and after addition of the reagent, the pH fell to 2-3, within which limits quantitative precipitation took place. As deduced from the break, the composition of the complex is 1:2, which is further confirmed by reverse titration (Fig. 1, curve B).

Titrant (ml).

FIG. 1

A— $M/1200$ uranyl nitrate (60 ml) vs. $M/25$ *N*-oxide,
B— $M/750$ *N*-oxide (60 ml) vs. $M/100$ uranyl nitrate.

Titrant (ml).

FIG. 2

$M/500$ uranyl nitrate (10 ml) vs.
 $M/25$ *N*-oxide.

The results of conductometric studies are shown in Fig. 2. In this case, uranyl salt solution was titrated against the reagent. The conductometric titration curve also shows that the composition of the complex is 1:2.

Gravimetric Determination of Uranium.—Solutions of different concentrations of uranyl nitrate were taken and about 2-3 times the theoretical quantity of the reagent in aqueous solution was added. For concentrations of $M/50$ or more of uranyl salt, pH was adjusted between 2.0 and 3.8 after addition of the precipitant. At lower concentrations of uranium ($\approx M/150$), complete precipitation took place only if pH was above 2.5. Below this pH, the results are low. The precipitate was allowed to settle for 3 to 4 hours, filtered through a sintered glass crucible G-4, washed with water, and dried in an oven at 120-40°. Uranium content was calculated from the formula UO_2A_2 . Results of some of the estimations are recorded in Table I. Correct results are also obtained by ignition of the complex to oxide.

TABLE I

Wt. of uranyl complex.

Calc. (mg.)	..	54.60	54.60	40.96	40.96	20.48	20.48
Found (mg.)	..	54.30	54.60	41.00	40.80	20.40	20.40
% Deviation	..	0.3	± 0.0	0.09	0.4	0.4	0.4

Separation of Uranium from other Metals.—Different amounts of thorium, lanthanum, vanadium, and zirconium salts were added to the uranyl salt solution and precipitation was carried out as described above. Thorium, lanthanum, and vanadium formed no

precipitate within the pH range of 2.0 and 3.8 and uranium could be estimated accurately in their presence. Zirconium, however, formed a white precipitate under the above conditions. When the combined precipitate of uranium and zirconium was boiled, the precipitate of zirconium complex dissolved, but the results obtained for uranium were low, thereby indicating partial solubility of the complex in boiling water. Heller *et al.*¹ however, have mentioned that uranium complex is insoluble in boiling aqueous solutions at pH 2-3. Results of some of the estimations in presence of other cations are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Foreign ion added,	Foreign salt (mg.).	Wt. of uranium complex.		
		Calc.	Found.	% Error.
Th(NO ₃) ₄	20.0 (ThO ₂)	54.60 mg.	54.60 mg.	Nil
"	14.5 "	54.60	54.80	0.30
La(NO ₃) ₃	39.0 (salt)	40.96	41.00	0.09
"	19.5 "	40.96	40.80	0.40
VOSO ₄	40.0 "	40.00	41.00	0.09
"	20.0 "	40.96	40.20	0.60

The above results show that the reagent is useful for determination of uranium in presence of a number of transition metals which form soluble complexes and hence they do not interfere.

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